

Management of Pregnancy, Labour and Neonatal Care with Homoeopathic Remedies

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ABSTRACT: In the current era, though the modern medical intervention in gestational period & labour reduce the maternal mortality rate to a greater extent, there prevails emerging issue of increasing c-section in deliveries. This is due to the fact that they keep on controlling the health of the mother under strong surveillance & medication which indirectly have its impact on mother's body thereby it lacks its natural mechanism or power to act on itself which gradually result in changing the labour from normal to C-section.

Homoeopathic remedies at gestational period & labour play a vital role in reducing the MMR & also reduce the complications which are arising during labour & improve health of mother & offspring in a natural way without disturbing the harmony of health.

KEY WORDS: Gestational period, Gestation, Homoeopathic remedies, Labour, MMR.

INTRODUCTION

During the gestational period, if any acute illness occur, the strong conventional drugs are contraindicated as they have short as well as long term effect on fetal development which result in fetal distress syndrome. Rather Homoeopathy remedies for treating any illness which are arising during early and late trimester of pregnancy such as fever, hyperemesis gravidarum, constipation, back ache, UTI, vaginal infection, anaemia, breast swelling haemorrhoids skin affections, varicose vein etc yield a good result and also enhance health of both mother and fetus.

Certain medical interventions of conventional medicine during labour are essential for safe birth no one can oppose that. But problem arise when these technologies & drugs are utilised in relatively normal pregnancy. Homoeopathic remedies during the last trimester & during labour play a vital role in reducing the need for this medical intervention and thus promote the normal delivery.

WHY HOMOEOPATHY FOR PREGNANCY

Labour pain is the first step in the birthing process of the neonate if the pain have not commenced beyond 42 weeks it is called prolonged labour. For these

conditions conventional mode of treatment practicing two methods to induce labour they were oxytocin infusion and amniotomy, while employing this amniotomy if the sac is not rupture properly means it result in leaking lot of fluid from the amniotic sac thereby reduce the cushion feeling for the fetus thus it pave way for c-section.

oxytocin infusion in conventional treatment though promotes the pain induction process in the harmless way as it can't replace the role of oxytocin secretion by mother's own body because the physiological process of any hormone secretion have positive as well as negative feedback mechanism which usually lacks at artificially induced oxytocin so it result in increased pain as it doesn't have any negative feedback to stop. Thereby it pave way for analgesia medication to reduce the pain & this analgesia further reduce the labour process by decreasing the uterine contraction.

Homoeopathic medication during last trimester promotes or assist the body to work on its own way by commencing labour pain and cervical ripening and cervical dilatation in the proper timings thus it reduce the need for modern medical interventions.

ROLE OF HOMOEOPATHY ON PREGNANCY

Homoeopathy has plenty of medicine based on symptom similarity for the complaint arising during the gestational period

HYPEREMESIS GRAVIDARUM

1. Ipeca --- nausea and vomiting with no amelioration throughout the day, As this drug have chief action on pneumogastric nerve especially indicated in fat , feeble, easily catch cold tendency women .Tongue usually clean with much salivation
- 2.Cocculus Indicus --- it is especially suited to night watching light hair women, vertigo and nausea especially while riding or sitting up, as soon as lifting the head from the pillow < taking cold , aversion to food and drink
3. Sepia --- waterbrash esp after drinking and eating. All gone sensation in the stomach , N ausea & vomiting feels better after eating and violent exercise
4. Nux vomica ---- it is best suited to thin nervous irritable individual , nausea want to vomit but cannot .Nausea & vomiting with much retching , feels better while lying down loves fat but tolerate them well Aconite 3x and bryonia 3x for every 30 minutes yield a best result

Homoeopathic Remedies For Last Trimester Of Pregnancy & During Labour

Even at the last trimester ,Homoeopathic remedy pulsatilla have the ability to correct the breech presentation as it act on the muscle of the uterus & thus enhance the stretchability of the uterine muscle thereby fetus assume the normal presentation & this remedy can be utilised if the placenta remain adherent to the uterus after the delivery. In this case it not only release the placenta but also tone up the uterus as to avoid post partum haemorrhage it is mentioned by DR. Farrington in his book clinical lectures of farrington

HOMOEOPATHIC REMEDIES DURING LABOUR

During labour homoeo remedies can be prescribed based on the expression of pain by the mother, Here I mention few remedies with its indicating symptoms

1. Kali carb --- At labour ward if the mother felt pain extremely in the small of the back which extend to the thigh with no marked pain in the uterus
2. Gelsemium --- In this remedy there is shifting type of pain as the pain running down the back & then it switch over to the uterus & again it moves towards the back with much weakness and cold sweat
3. Actea racinosa ---- In this remedy the pain moves across the sides of the abdomen (esp across the broad ligament of uterus) & mother have the pessimistic idea about delivery & pain felt like electric shock throughout the body from the uterus
4. Caulophyllum --- It strengthened the uterine muscle at last trimester & during labour it dilate the undilated cervix & soften the rigid cervix & promotes uterine contraction
5. Pulsatilla & secale cor --- these remedies are indicated if the cervix is dilated & there is no commencement of uterine contraction or else if irregular contraction of uterus present

POST PARTUM HOMOEOPATHIC REMEDIES:

After delivery if the placenta remain adherent to the uterus homoeo remedies such as caulophyllum, belladonna, cantharis, secale cornutum, pulsatilla Sabina can be used based on symptom similarity as the remedies not only treat the condition but also strengthened the uterine muscles

1. Arnica --- this remedy is useful especially after the c-section as it have the capacity to reduce the shock & traumatic effect of the surgery and thus reduce the soreness feeling of the body
2. Staphysagria – it is excellent remedy given after any surgery to reduce the pain so it can reduce the usage of analgesia after delivery
3. Bellis perenallis --- it works on internal injuries especially for perenium tear during labour
4. Sulphur --- It can able to prevent the infection of bladder, vagina & infection over surgical suture
5. Calendula Q – it can applied over the episiotomy suture ,as it hasten the healing process

Antibiotics and analgesia of conventional treatment have its influence on neonates health through breast feeding the neonates liver lacks the power to detoxify the effect of these drugs which to a minute degree has it influence on health of new born in future

HOMOEOPATHY ROLE IN NEONATAL CARE

In neonatal care while taking homoeopathic remedies along with the emergency medical measures it increase the survival rate of the neonates.

1. Anti tart -- it removes the sudden blockage of phlegm in the throat and chest & there is much rattling in the chest with difficulty in breathing
2. Carbo veg --- it is indicated if the new born is cold , blue & there is reduced oxidation process in venous circulation with feeble respiration
3. Camphor --- It is indicated if the neonate have fever with much vomiting and diarrhoea the newborn present with the symptoms of dehydration and there is marked redness over the abdomen and thigh
4. Arnica --- it is indicated in haematoma of new born as this remedy have the power to reduce the haematoma after tramatic delivery. Arnica is followed well by rhus tox
5. Nux vomica – For neonatal jaundice it helps to reduce the bilirubin values in 2or 3 days aconite can also be used thus it reduce the incubator period of neonates

CONCLUSION

Homoeopathic remedies there by assist or support the mothers body during labour and gestational period to exercise on its own principal without any hindrance to the natural way of labour

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